

Show Me How to Play: Exploring Self-Modeling for Onboarding in Virtual Reality Exergames

Sukran Karaosmanoglu
Human-Computer Interaction
Universität Hamburg
Hamburg, Germany
sukran.karaosmanoglu@uni-hamburg.de

Silas Ueberschaer
Human-Computer Interaction
Universität Hamburg
Hamburg, Germany
silas.ueberschaer@studium.uni-hamburg.de

Sebastian Cmentowski
Industrial Design
Eindhoven University of Technology
Eindhoven, Netherlands
s.cmentowski@tue.nl

Frank Steinicke
Human-Computer Interaction
Universität Hamburg
Hamburg, Germany
frank.steinicke@uni-hamburg.de

Figure 1: An illustration showing a player engaging with the *BoxPunchVR* game, using different punches to hit blocks that appear on three stands. Each block type corresponds to a specific punch direction.

Abstract

Exergames combine motivating game elements with bodily movement to encourage physical activity. However, onboarding players to perform correct movements remains a challenge, especially in virtual reality (VR) environments where safety and performance are critical. Drawing inspiration from sports training and learning sciences, we contrast two onboarding approaches: (i) trial-and-error and (ii) observational learning via a novel self-model tutorial. In this tutorial, players temporarily lose agency and observe their own avatar performing the movements, leveraging VR's unique affordances for embodied experiences. To explore which of these

two approaches yields a better performance and player experience, we conducted a between-participants study ($N = 60$), comparing them against a baseline condition without a tutorial. Our findings show that the self-model tutorial not only improves players' performance but also increases the perceived ease of control and progress feedback. We discuss tradeoffs and implications for the design of future onboarding experiences in VR exergames.

CCS Concepts

• Human-centered computing → Virtual reality; Empirical studies in HCI; • Software and its engineering → Interactive games.

Keywords

virtual reality, exergames, exercise games, movement-based games, tutorials, onboarding, embodiment, agency, avatar

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. CHI '26, Barcelona, Spain

© 2026 Copyright held by the owner/author(s).
ACM ISBN 979-8-4007-2278-3/26/04
<https://doi.org/10.1145/3772318.3790333>

ACM Reference Format:

Sukran Karaosmanoglu, Silas Ueberschaer, Sebastian Cmentowski, and Frank Steinicke. 2026. Show Me How to Play: Exploring Self-Modeling for Onboarding in Virtual Reality Exergames. In *Proceedings of the 2026 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI '26)*, April 13–17, 2026, Barcelona, Spain. ACM, New York, NY, USA, 16 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3772318.3790333>

1 Introduction

Even though physical activity has numerous health- and well-being-related benefits [99, 100], insufficient physical activity remains a growing problem of modern society [100]. Some of the reasons for this physical inactivity include lacking motivation and limited access to exercise opportunities [67]. Aiming for engaging and motivating exercises, virtual reality (VR) exergames have been proposed that can even be played from the comfort of one's home. These blend physical exercise, for example, boxing, dancing, or strength moves [28, 95], into immersive gameplay to offer playful-like exercising options [68]. Research indicates that VR exergames can enhance motivation and lead to higher performance compared to conventional forms of play, such as on TV displays [8, 101]. However, despite these advantages, there are also potential risks associated with their use.

Although their immersive and captivating nature can enhance motivation and enjoyment in exergames, VR head-mounted displays (HMDs) create additional design challenges, particularly due to them blocking the users' view of the physical real world. Wearing a VR HMD in exercising contexts can increase the risk of collisions, making it challenging to ensure safety [22]. Even without accidents, their movement-centered gameplay makes these games more prone to injuries and overstraining if players do not perform the movements correctly. Since some of these safety issues are likely caused by players not playing the game as intended or executing movements incorrectly, we believe that onboarding players in the experience is an important, fundamental step toward ensuring safe and beneficial VR exergaming.

Games typically onboard players using tutorials [97]. These teach players both the gameplay mechanics as well as safe movement execution (e.g., [20, 48]). According to White [97], there are two primary types of tutorial teaching methods: (i) “*exploratory*” and (ii) “*didactic*”. The exploratory approach encourages players to learn through trial and error by exploring actions independently, without direct instructions. In contrast, the didactic approach involves guiding players by providing explicit instructions for completing tasks, which can be delivered in various formats. For example, this can be achieved by providing demonstration-based instructions, following the *worked-example effect* [97], which a learner can observe. While prior studies have explored various aspects of VR game tutorials, including context-sensitive design [31], time manipulations [14], and modalities [42], no prior research has yet explored the effects of *exploratory versus demonstration-based* tutorials for VR exergames.

To design an exploratory tutorial, we draw on the trial-and-error theory by Thorndike [91]. This theory suggests that learning occurs through experimenting with different possibilities and experiencing the consequences until a desired outcome is achieved [82, 91]. Since this approach conceptually aligns with the classification proposed by White [97] on exploratory tutorials and allows players to

learn by exploring possibilities and their outcomes independently without receiving explicit guidance, we based our exploratory tutorial's design on this theory and named it the *trial-and-error tutorial (T&E)*. Accordingly, in this tutorial, we did not provide any instructions to our players. They performed actions freely, experienced whether their actions were successful or not, and learned through completing this process.

Observational learning is supported by neuroscience research [10, 94] and has been widely recognized as one of the most effective methods for learning [4, 5]. According to social learning theory [4, 5], behaviors can be learned through modeling, where individuals observe a model performing a task and then imitate it. For example, a model might demonstrate which color of cup to select to find a reward, allowing a learner to observe the pattern and imitate it [4]. However, research indicates that learners tend to prefer to learn from models that are similar to themselves and perceive as relatable [4, 18]. In traditional sports, this concept can be utilized by recording athletes' movements and replaying their own best performances, which has been named *self-modeling* [18].

Motivated by Kao et al. [42]'s notion that tutorials should be designed based on the intended game genre, we believe that the effectiveness of self-modeling could be further improved by using the unique affordances of immersive VR experiences, in particular the concept of embodiment [50, 77]. Accordingly, in our demonstration-based tutorial, we base our design on a novel concept that disembodies players from their own avatar and uses it to demonstrate the correct movements—allowing players to observe their own disembodied self (i.e., *self-model*). We achieve this by making the player's arm avatars semi-transparent to indicate a loss of agency, thereby creating a “ghost” effect. The ghost arms then move away from the player to complete a tutorial, and after completion, they return to the player's control. Given the combined effects of virtual body ownership [51, 55, 56, 86] and observational learning [4, 18, 63], we assume that this immersive self-model observation can further enhance players' performance by encouraging them to imitate the observed movements. While prior work has examined the use of ghost avatars in VR self-competition contexts [3, 6, 26, 66, 83], the application of the self-as-a-model within VR exergames, specifically in tutorials, remains unexplored. This gap motivates us to explore the *self-model* tutorial (*GHOST*) as an innovative tutorial approach.

To summarize, building on the tutorial classification proposed by White [97], our study introduces and compares two distinct onboarding experiences: an exploratory versus a demonstration-based tutorial. The exploratory tutorial (*T&E*) encourages players to explore the game mechanics independently and learn through direct interaction without receiving instructions (designed based on trial-and-error theory [82, 91]). The second tutorial uses our novel *self-model* concept (*GHOST*), which leverages observational learning (i.e., social learning theory of Bandura [4] and findings from self-modeling in sports sciences [18]). In this tutorial, players temporarily lose agency of their avatar and observe their avatar's movements completing correct actions. Since prior research suggests that every game may not require a tutorial [2], we also included a control condition without a tutorial (*BASE*) to test the impact of both onboarding approaches on the player experience and performance. Taken together, we answer the following research questions:

- **RQ1:** How do the tutorial conditions (*GHOST* and *T&E*) influence players' experience and performance compared to the no tutorial (*BASE*) condition?
- **RQ2:** How does the self-model tutorial (*GHOST*) influence players' experience and performance compared to the trial-and-error tutorial (*T&E*)?

To answer our research questions, we conducted a between-participants study with three conditions: (i) *self-model tutorial* (*GHOST*), (ii) *trial-and-error tutorial* (*T&E*), and (iii) a control condition with *no tutorial* (*BASE*). Our results from 60 participants ($n=20$ in each condition) suggest that the temporary disembodiment of the *GHOST* condition did not significantly reduce perceived body ownership and agency compared to the other conditions. Instead, participants perceived the *GHOST* approach as more meaningful and informative, experienced greater ease of controls, and demonstrated higher accuracy in game performance compared to both *T&E* and *BASE*. Although *T&E* also led to significantly higher ease of control and accuracy than *BASE*, only *GHOST* was found to be more motivating. Participants evaluated the usefulness of the *GHOST* tutorial significantly higher than that of *T&E*. Qualitative feedback further supported the notion that tutorials are important in VR exergames. Overall, the findings suggest that the *GHOST* tutorial method enhances player experience, perceived usefulness, motivation, and gameplay accuracy, without causing significantly higher disruption in virtual embodiment compared to other conditions. We discuss the trade-offs and implications for designing tutorials in VR exergames to promote learnability and positive player experiences. Specifically, we emphasize the potential of transitional embodiment, encourage the exploration of player-sensitive tutorials, and recommend further investigation of tutorial designs grounded in additional learning theories. Taken together, we summarize our paper's contributions following the classification of human-computer interaction research contributions [98]:

- (1) We provide artifact contributions [98] by presenting the design of two tutorials as well as a VR exergame.
- (2) We investigate how exploratory and demonstration-based tutorials affect player experience and performance in VR exergames and provide empirical insights [98].
- (3) We conclude our paper with a theoretical contribution [98] by discussing our results in relation to previous work and providing research and design implications for creating VR exergame tutorials.

2 Related Work

This section highlights the benefits and challenges of VR exergames, gives an overview of relevant learning theories, demonstrates the potential of VR to induce virtual body embodiment, and emphasizes the importance of tutorials for player onboarding in VR games.

2.1 VR Exergames

VR exergames have the potential to promote physical exercise by combining it with immersive gameplay [43]. Unlike traditional video games, where players control on-screen characters, VR exergames enable players to embody a character and perform physical exercises from a first-person perspective. For example, instead of

performing boxing movements in front of a TV, players can take the role of a boxer (see FitXR [28]). Prior research has explored exergames with a wide variety of physical activities, such as running [40, 102], jumping [20, 40], upper-body workouts [45, 46], and various playful sports experiences [53, 66, 80]. Beyond replicating real-world movements, VR exergames open up unique possibilities that would be impossible otherwise. For instance, these games can give players hyperrealistic jumping abilities [40], enable superhuman punching power [9], offer exaggerated cycling speed [64], or transport users to environments they may not be able to access due to their health limitations [46, 57]. Taken together, these games not only widen the scope of what is possible in playful exercise but also have been shown to significantly boost users' motivation and physical performance [8, 101].

Although VR exergames provide motivation to exercise, there are also potential risks with their use. While many VR applications carry the risk of collisions or injuries due to the VR HMD blocking the player's view [22], these concerns are increased by the larger and faster movements in exergames. For example, while Cmentowski et al. [20] received positive feedback regarding the player experience and usability for their VR jump-training exergame, the authors also highlighted the risk of injuries from incorrect movement executions and from potential collisions due to unintended forward movements during jumps. Research on collision anxiety in VR games [75, 76] further indicates that larger, wider movements can impact users' concern about collisions. Chiu et al. [16] interviewed physical therapists about the use of a commercial VR exergame for physical therapy, underscoring the importance of integrating feedback or guidance to prevent harm (e.g., re-injury). While there are general methods in VR to reduce safety risks, such as boundary systems [93] and overlays [79], the faster and more extensive movements that are part of VR exergames may heighten the risk of safety concerns [75]. Further, Tseng et al. [93] reported that people can disregard VR safety boundaries on purpose. Overall, these safety considerations and recommendations highlight the importance of prioritizing user safety when designing VR exergames. Accordingly, as an important first step, we focus on tutorials that can help onboard players toward learning to perform movements correctly in VR exergames.

2.2 From Learning Behaviors to Tutorials

According to White [97], tutorials teach players how to play the game and can come in various forms and modalities, for example, interactive tutorial levels and on-screen text interactions. However, tutorials can be divided primarily into two teaching methods: (i) exploratory and (ii) didactic. The exploratory methods allow players to learn by trying and failing without providing instructions. In didactic tutorials, players are provided guidance on how game mechanics work. When looking at these methods through the lens of learning theories, the exploratory approach aligns with trial-and-error learning principles [82]. For the didactic method, we draw on observational learning, where players can acquire knowledge by observing demonstrations [4].

The trial-and-error theory, proposed by Thorndike [91], suggests that people learn by attempting actions and observing the outcomes [82]. In simple terms, learners make a choice first; if this

choice does not produce a positive result, they try alternative options. Through this process, learners identify the successful choices. This theory is based on three fundamental principles: (i) the law of readiness, which reflects the learner's preparedness to learn; (ii) the law of exercise, which involves strengthening the links between actions and their outcomes through practice; and (iii) the law of effect, which states that behaviors followed by positive outcomes are more likely to be learned, while those followed by negative outcomes are not learned [82]. Given the trial-and-error learning's widespread use [41, 71, 74], particularly in sport contexts [61, 92] we chose this approach as one of the tutorial conditions.

To understand how to didactically teach gameplay mechanics, we draw upon the social learning theory [4, 5], which explains how individuals learn behaviors. According to this theory [4, 5], “*virtually all learning phenomena resulting from direct experiences can occur on a vicarious basis through observation of other people's behavior and its consequences for them*”. In essence, the theory argues that observing the actions and outcomes experienced by others allows people to learn new behaviors without relying solely on trial and error. For observational learning to occur, Bandura [4] outlines four essential cognitive subprocesses: (i) attention, (ii) retention, (iii) motor reproduction, and (iv) reinforcement and motivation. First, the model's behavior must catch the attention of the learner. Next, learners must be able to remember what they observed. Then, they must have the capability to reproduce the model's behavior themselves. Finally, the decision to imitate the behavior depends on whether the observed consequences are perceived as beneficial or detrimental. If the positive outcomes outweigh any negatives, the individual would imitate the modeled behavior. Overall, observational learning has a well-established presence in literature [4, 5] with demonstrated effectiveness across various contexts. It has been applied in education [35], sports [18, 63] and supported with neuroscience research [10, 94]. The similarity between a model and the learner is a significant factor influencing learning behavior and performance [4, 18, 60]. Ultimately, the most similar model to oneself is again oneself. In this context, Dowrick [25] define self-modeling as “*an intervention procedure using the observation of images of oneself engaged in adaptive behavior*”. Self-modeling can be achieved by recording oneself performing an activity and then editing the footage to remove errors, thereby highlighting the individual's best performance. For example, Clark and Ste-Marie [18] found that self-modeling improved performance and supported learning motor skills. Inspired by this observational modeling approach, we explore the applicability of this method in VR exergames, considering the use of a virtual avatar as a representation of oneself.

2.3 Presence and Sense of Embodiment in VR

Since VR HMDs allow users to experience virtual environments through head-based input (e.g., moving the head) and provide stereoscopic views, these systems are considered immersive, reflecting their technical capabilities [32, 85]. Such highly immersive systems, which deliver high-quality visuals and audio, can evoke a sense of presence and give users the feeling of being in the virtual environment [84, 85, 87].

Due to its immersive qualities, VR not only creates a sense of presence within a virtual environment but can also enable a sense

of embodiment, defined as an “*ensemble of sensations that arise in conjunction with being inside, having, and controlling a body*” [50]. Embodiment has three subcomponents: (i) *sense of self-location*, (ii) *agency*, and (iii) *body ownership*. The sense of self-location refers to the feeling of presence within a specific body. The sense of agency concerns the perception of control over one's actions, while body ownership relates to the feeling that the body is one's own.

In VR, a sense of embodiment can be achieved by using virtual avatars that represent the user. Research indicates that users can respond to actions aimed at their virtual avatars as if they were happening to their own physical bodies [34, 51]. For example, in the study by González-Franco et al. [34], participants exposed to an attack on their virtual hand exhibited motor cortex activation similar to what is expected if their own real hand were threatened. Beyond avatars that are similar in size or appearance to the users, some studies have shown that users can feel virtual body ownership with avatars differing in aspects such as gender [86], race [72], limb length [51], and even species [55, 56]. For instance, Krekhov et al. [55] found that animal avatars can also induce a sense of virtual body ownership. Given the potential of VR to induce a sense of virtual body ownership, we specifically focus on designing a tutorial that integrates observational learning with embodied self-modeling for VR exergames.

2.4 Tutorials in VR and VR Games

Almost all commercial VR exergames incorporate some form of tutorial to onboard players; for a general overview of onboarding in VR applications, see [13]. For instance, *Beat Saber* features an interactive tutorial with text instructions [33]. Many academic studies on VR exergaming note that they provide tutorials before onboarding players into gameplay (e.g., [20, 48]). However, only a limited number of research papers investigate the effects of tutorials in VR games [14, 31, 42, 59].

Both Frommel et al. [31] and Kao et al. [42] note the increasing accessibility of VR to users and emphasize the limited exploration of tutorial design in VR games. Frommel et al. [31] compared a context-sensitive tutorial, where instructions are provided at moments when players need to interact with game mechanics, with a traditional instruction screen tutorial in a VR wave shooter game. They found that context-sensitive tutorials enhance player motivation, while overall player performance remains comparable between the two approaches. Chen et al. [14] investigated four different tutorial modes that varied by their time flow rates: traditional instruction screen, slow motion (where the player moves and the game slows down), bullet time (where the player moves at normal speed but the game slows down), and context-sensitive modes. They found that the bullet time mode improved controls learnability and player performance while also reducing players' cognitive load. Kao et al. [42] examined the effects of three different modalities (i.e., text only, text with diagram, text with spatial reference) across four VR games. Their results indicated that the impact of modality is specific to the game genre. For example, in a VR third-person shooter, text with spatial reference improved controls learnability, whereas in a VR rhythm game, there was no significant effect of modality type. Similarly, in video game research, Andersen et al. [2] pointed out a game-specific aspect: game complexity. The authors demonstrated

that tutorials can increase play time in a complex game (i.e., a puzzle game that requires manipulating protein structures), but this effect is not observed in simpler games (i.e., casual puzzle games). Given that VR exergames incorporate not only cognitive elements but also involve physical tasks, these games may require genre-specific approaches in their tutorial design.

Observational learning has been applied in VR environments [12, 24, 27]. For example, Dietz et al. [24] compared a gamification approach (collecting virtual objects) with an imitation approach (following an expert model) to assist users in maintaining their balance during a height beam-walking task. In their study, a ghost avatar representing an expert (a slack-line expert) was shown walking on the beam in front of the users, who were instructed to imitate the behavior of this avatar. Their findings indicated that the imitation method outperformed the gamification approach in improving balance control. Similarly, Cannavò et al. [12] developed a VR self-learning tool aimed at enhancing basketball free throw skills by showing the optimal throwing technique through a ghost avatar. Their comparisons between the VR system and a projection-based system revealed that users favored the VR system. Using a puzzle task, Fitton et al. [27] found that the observational learning approach combined with practice for fine motor skill training in VR can be beneficial, leading us to focus on observational learning.

In VR exergames, ghost avatars are commonly used for self-competition purposes [3, 26, 66, 83]. For example, Shaw et al. [83] found that players competing against a ghost avatar of their previous performance resulted in greater distances traveled and increased enjoyment compared to competing with a virtual trainer exhibiting optimal behavior. Similar to Shaw et al. [83], Barathi et al. [6] also examined the self-model in a competition context. Their findings showed that players performed better when competing against a ghost avatar representing their enhanced previous performance, as opposed to competing against a ghost avatar of their earlier performance or a non-self model ghost avatar (i.e., a virtual competitor). In a longitudinal study, Michael and Lutteroth [66] examined the impact of multi-ghost competition, where participants raced against multiple ghost avatars representing their past performances as well as an improved future performance based on participants' own best performance. Their findings indicated that multi-ghost competition outperformed the non-competitive version of the game in terms of performance, exertion, and motivation. While these studies highlight the potential of using ghost avatars and users' identification with them as reflections of their own self, to our knowledge, ghost avatars as a self-model have not yet been explored in VR exergames for tutorial purposes.

2.5 Research Gap

Taken together, prior research emphasizes the importance of providing proper onboarding to players to ensure both enjoyment and safety. However, it remains unclear which methods are best for achieving these goals, including their advantages and disadvantages. Building upon established learning theories [4, 5, 82, 91], embodiment research [50, 85], as well as the positive outcomes of using self-model concepts in VR exergames [6, 66, 83], we have developed a novel self-model tutorial that utilizes a ghost metaphor

to visually demonstrate correct movement patterns through self-model observational learning, and we compare this approach with a traditional trial-and-error method. Previous work in VR exergames with ghost avatars [6, 66, 83] has explored competition using one's own previous performance, enhanced performance, or multiple performance points. However, in these studies, players retained continuous agency over their current avatar. To the best of our knowledge, our work is the first to investigate the application of the self-model concept specifically for instructional purposes, while also temporarily removing agency using ghost metaphor. Consequently, we present the first empirical findings comparing exploratory and demonstration-based VR exergame tutorials.

3 Exergame: BoxPunchVR

To compare the two selected tutorial modes and answer our research questions, we started our research by creating a suitable single-player exergame: *BoxPunchVR*. The game was developed using Unity (v.2022.3.33f1) [90] and uses a Meta Quest 3 headset and controllers [65].

3.1 Game Design Rationale and Gameplay

Following exergame research guidelines [43], we report on the game's purpose, target audience, exercises, and design. With *BoxPunchVR*, we aimed to promote physical activity while providing both cognitive and physical training. The target audience for the game was young and middle-aged adults who could safely perform upper body movements while standing. In terms of exercises, our game featured upper body exercises primarily involving arm (e.g., punches) and light torso movements. We specifically used a mobile VR headset (i.e., Meta Quest 3 [65]) to avoid potential cable-related safety challenges.

Our primary focus was on evaluating the impact of the tutorials, which motivated and shaped the design of the VR exergame. To determine the type of tasks to use in our game, we reviewed the literature and existing exergames. The findings of a recent review on extended reality exergames [43] led us to use target-based tasks (e.g., punching blocks), as these tasks are the most common ones used in exergames. Similarly, many exergames, such as FitXR [28] and Black Box VR [95], offer boxing-themed experiences. Therefore, we decided to focus on target-based tasks in the form of a boxing-themed exercise game to increase the study's external validity.

During the gameplay, players find themselves in a gym-like VR environment set within a boxing ring. As the main in-game action, players have to use a variety of punches to hit blocks spawned on three stands in the players' proximity. The correct punch for each block is indicated by abstract symbols on the respective block. We drew inspiration from regular boxing, since it provides a certain degree of familiarity to players; generally, the game's theme and blocks provide cues about the action possibilities (i.e., punching) that players can take in each condition—a common concept known as “affordance” [70]. As a result, we avoid overly frustrating players in the *BASE* group. At the same time, players still need to learn the coding between the different symbols and associated punches, requiring them to create a mental model for succeeding in the game. While the ultimate goal of an ideal game design is to be as intuitive as possible, we purposefully incorporated this associative

Figure 2: Our game includes three types of blocks, each designed to be punched in specific ways. ○ blocks must be hit with a right hook, △ with a left hook, and □ with a jab using either hand.

concept to create a testing ground for the tutorials that mimics more complex games featuring novel concepts within the confinements of a controlled study. To keep the game simple, we selected two primary boxing moves, the jab and the hook, and designed three different block types (see Figure 2):

- (1) Jab: The blocks with □ signs could be punched from the front using either hand.
- (2) Hook (right): The blocks with ○ signs had to be hit with a right hook, i.e., punched from the right side with the right hand.
- (3) Hook (left): The blocks with △ sign had to be hit with a left hook, i.e., punched from the left side with the left hand.

When a punch is registered, audio feedback is provided to indicate whether the block has been hit. If the punch direction matches the required direction for the block, the block flies away and disappears, causing the next block to fall down in a tetris-like style (i.e., positive feedback). Otherwise, the block does not move and stays (i.e., negative feedback). To detect the correct direction of hits, we added colliders to the left, right, and front of the blocks and checked if those and the block itself were hit by the correct arm in quick succession (i.e., <0.5 seconds). To avoid missing correct punches, we scaled the colliders such that they permit a punch direction tolerance of 36.4° . To induce more movement variety, we added three platforms where blocks are spawned: to the front, as well as on the right and the left side of the player (see Figure 1). The sequence as well as the types of blocks were predetermined to ensure comparability across conditions (see the supplementary materials for the used block sequence in the tutorials and gameplays).

3.2 Tutorials

Drawing on the classification of tutorial types [97], we designed one exploratory and one demonstration-based tutorial. The exploratory tutorial, *T&E*, requires the player to actively interact with virtual objects (i.e., blocks) using a trial-and-error approach without any instructions [82, 91]. In *GHOST*, players see self-as-a-model and engage in observational learning [4, 18].

3.2.1 Trial-and-error tutorial. In this exploratory tutorial [97], participants can interactively engage with the game mechanics before the gameplay. The tutorial is designed to highlight the principles of trial-and-error learning theory [82, 91], where players respond to stimuli presented in front of them (i.e., blocks) and learn through the process of trying different actions and receiving feedback, whether

positive (i.e., the block flies away and disappears) or negative (i.e., the block stays), to guide their future responses and learning.

The tutorial section presents 12 blocks and allows players to learn the game’s punch mechanism in four phases. First, players punch three triangle blocks placed in front of them, which require a left hook (see Figure 3b). Next, players see three circle blocks on the left, requiring right hooks. In the third phase, players see three square blocks on the right stand that require them to punch from the front using either hand. Finally, players practice the combination of these three block types that appear in front of them.

3.2.2 Self-model tutorial. In this tutorial, participants engage in an observation-based self-model learning experience. This approach is rooted in the principles of self-model observational learning [4, 5, 18, 63]. To support this method, we leverage virtual embodiment [51, 55, 56, 86] by providing participants with virtual arms. Since our game primarily emphasizes arm-based interaction, we use virtual arms instead of a full-body avatar to minimize potential distractions that might arise from users exploring their full-body avatar during the tutorial, which could negatively impact the learning process. Over four seconds, during which participants can familiarize themselves with the perspective, the arms gradually become semi-transparent, signaling virtual disembodiment and a loss of agency. Then, the “ghost” arms start performing the tutorial. In this phase, similar to self-model learning approaches that showcase one’s own best performances [18, 63], participants observe correct punch interactions. Matching the *T&E* tutorial, the “ghost” interacts with the same 12 blocks by punching them in the correct direction (see Figure 3c, also see the supplementary video material for demonstrations). Once the four phases have been completed, the arm control gradually returns back to participants, and the arms become opaque again within four seconds.

4 User Study

To answer your research questions, we conducted an exploratory between-participants user study with three conditions: (i) *BASE*, (ii) *T&E*, and (iii) *GHOST*. We particularly chose a between-participants design to avoid potential learning effects, which could affect player experience and performance. Since our study was exploratory and, to our knowledge, there are no prior studies comparing tutorials based on learning theories in VR exergames, we followed the recommendation of Caine [11] regarding sample size in HCI research. Consequently, we consolidated similar studies from the literature [14, 24, 31, 42] to inform our decision on an appropriate sample size. As a result, we recruited a total of 60 participants, evenly distributing them across the three conditions ($n=20$).

4.1 Conditions

Our study included three conditions to which participants were randomly assigned:

- (1) **No tutorial** — *BASE*: In this condition, participants were not given any tutorial before the gameplay of five minutes. They encountered the block sequence directly during play, without any prior practice or demonstration, aside from being informed that they would be playing in a boxing game.

Figure 3: The impressions from the different phases of the study. a) In the calibration step, a player calibrates their virtual arm length using two buttons, allowing them to match the position of their real elbow with the virtual elbow. b) In the *T&E* condition, a player performs an exploratory trial-and-error approach. c) In the *GHOST* condition, a player temporarily loses control of their avatar and observes themselves as a semi-transparent “ghost” performing movements (i.e., self-as-a-model). The semi-transparency indicates that the player is currently not in control of the avatar.

- (2) **Trial-and-error tutorial** – *T&E*: This condition involves experiencing a tutorial designed based on trial-and-error principles [82, 91], followed by an identical five-minute gameplay session as in the *BASE* condition.
- (3) **Self-model tutorial** – *GHOST*: This condition covers experiencing the self-model tutorial [4, 5, 18, 63], followed by an identical gameplay session as in the *BASE* and *T&E* conditions.

4.2 Measures

In our study, we collected psychometric, physiological, and in-game performance metrics. Since our study is exploratory by nature, it is positioned as hypothesis-generating research rather than confirmatory research. Given that the work intersects with VR, exergames, and learning research, we use metrics in line with the methodological practices of these fields. For example, punch accuracy in our study serves as an indicator of short-term learning outcomes and can be conceptually linked to learning theories: In social learning theory [4, 5], it reflects the degree of imitation following modeling, whereas in Thorndike [91]’s trial-and-error theory, it represents refinement through repeated attempts. Similarly, gaining a comprehensive understanding of how tutorials or the absence of tutorials affect player experience in VR exergames offers insights into the psychological and functional outcomes of these experiences [1]. Together, these measures allow us to explore how different tutorial approaches (*BASE*, *T&E*, *GHOST*) influence players’ experiential and performance-related outcomes in a holistic and theoretically informed manner, enabling us to answer **RQ1** and **RQ2**.

4.2.1 Pre-Game Questionnaire. We obtained sample characteristics using a demographic questionnaire asking about participants’ age, gender, technology use, and exercising habits. We used the Simulator Sickness Questionnaire (SSQ) [38, 49] to assess the prior cybersickness symptoms before the gameplay; it has a total of 16

items on a 4-point scale (*none/0* – *severe/3*), leading to a total SSQ, nausea, oculomotor disturbance, and disorientation score.

4.2.2 Post-Game Questionnaire. We again used the SSQ to ensure that our game and tutorial methods did not induce a significant increase in cybersickness symptoms. To assess whether disembodiment might disrupt participants’ experience, we administered the Virtual Embodiment Questionnaire (VEQ) [77], particularly the acceptance / body ownership and control / agency subcategories, to measure participants’ perceptions about their virtual body. Each subcategory includes four items on a 7-point Likert scale (*strongly disagree/1* – *strongly agree/7*). Since virtual embodiment might be related to presence in VR [50], we used the IGroup Presence Questionnaire (IPQ) [81]. The questionnaire measures perceived presence across 14 items rated on a 7-point scale (*fully disagree/-3* – *fully agree/+3*), resulting in general presence, spatial presence, involvement, and experienced realism scores.

To understand whether the type or presence of tutorials affects motivation, we assessed the players’ interest/enjoyment (i.e., motivation) using the Intrinsic Motivation Inventory (IMI) [78] (seven items on a 7-point Likert scale, *not at all true/1* – *very true/7*). The player experience was assessed using the Player Experience Inventory (PXI) [1] to get a comprehensive overview of changes in the player experience. We used all subcategories of the PXI, consisting of 30 items on a 7-point Likert scale (*strongly disagree/-3* – *strongly agree/+3*). In addition to game enjoyment, we also measured players’ physical activity enjoyment using the short version of the Physical Activity Enjoyment Scale (PACES-S) [15, 30] (four items on a 5-point Likert scale (*strongly disagree/1* – *strongly agree/5*), as type of tutorial or lack thereof might affect the enjoyment of the activity.

Lastly, we employed the NASA-Task Load Index (NASA-TLX) [37], which measures six dimensions (e.g., mental demand) of perceived workload¹, to evaluate how the tutorials influence the

¹The NASA-TLX performance item was reverse-coded for analysis; higher scores indicate perceived higher success.

Figure 4: The between-participants study procedure followed in our research. The participants played one of the randomly assigned conditions. We assessed the questionnaire, game performance, and heart rate data.

perceived demand of the experience. Participants rated each dimension on a 21-point Likert scale (e.g., *very low/0* – *very high/100*). To measure the perceived usefulness of the tutorials (i.e., *BASE* and *GHOST*), participants who were assigned to one of the tutorial conditions rated four 7-point Likert scale items (*strongly disagree/1* – *strongly agree/7*), which were used in a previous VR games tutorial study [31], see the exact phrasings of the items in the supplementary material. Finally, all participants were provided with an open-ended question to answer in written form: “*Do you have any additional comments?*”.

4.2.3 Physiological Measures. We used a Polar OH1+ armband (1 Hz) to measure participants’ heart rate metrics to understand their objective exertion (similar to other VR exergame studies [8, 40]). Following previous studies [47], the heart rate metrics were collected for five minutes and then averaged to obtain the baseline heart rate measurement. Similarly to the baseline measurement, we also calculated the heart rate during gameplay by averaging the raw heart rate metrics measured using the same armband.

4.2.4 Game Performance Measures. During the gameplay, we collected game performance measures: physical activity and number of correct and incorrect hits. Physical activity was calculated by summing the total distance of position changes of the right and left hand controllers. The punch accuracy was calculated by dividing the number of correct hits by the total amount of punches performed by the participant.

4.3 Participants

Sixty participants were recruited for our study (31 women, 29 men, age: $M=26.92$, $SD=7.47$, $Min-Max=19 - 56$).

Game & VR Experience. Seven participants reported not playing digital games at all, while the remaining participants engaged in digital gameplay with varying frequency: every day ($n = 11$), often (1-2 times per week, $n = 12$), frequently (1-2 times per month, $n = 11$), rarely (1-2 times per year, $n = 15$), or seldomly (1-2 times total, $n = 4$). Participants were not frequent VR users. Twenty-four participants had never used VR-based applications, while 31 participants reported using VR at most rarely (1-2 times per year).

Physical Activity Experience. Our sample moderately enjoyed exercising ($M=1.32$, $SD=147$) and can be considered moderately active: Thirty-five participants exercised at least 1-2 times per week, while remaining participants exercised with lower frequency: 1-2 times per month, ($n = 17$), 1-2 times per year ($n = 6$), or never ($n = 2$). In contrast, participants reported little to no experience with boxing or combat sports: never ($n=30$), seldom (1-2 times in total, $n = 16$), or rarely (1-2 times per year, $n = 7$), frequently (1-2 times per month, $n = 2$), often (1-2 times per week, $n = 5$).

4.4 Procedure

We advertised our study through university email lists, the university’s recruitment platform, and our personal networks.

At the beginning of the study, participants were asked to read and sign a consent form that introduces the study. Next, participants completed the pre-game questionnaires asking about demographic information and cybersickness symptoms. Then, they wore the heart rate armband on their non-dominant arm and were asked to sit still without talking for five minutes to obtain the baseline heart rate metrics. Afterwards, participants were assigned to one of the study conditions: *BASE*, *T&E*, and *GHOST*. Next, participants were instructed on how to wear the VR HMD, provided with controllers, and given time to familiarize themselves with the VR HMD and controllers. Once they confirmed their comfort, we started the application and provided instructions on how to calibrate the virtual arm length. While the calibration did not have any influence on the gameplay, an optical fit between real and virtual body is important for body ownership [62]. To adjust their virtual arm, participants used a VR user interface, which provided two buttons that controlled the arm length, allowing them to match the position of their real elbow with the virtual elbow (see Figure 3a and supplementary video material). Once participants confirmed the alignment of their real and virtual elbows, they pressed the confirm button to indicate that they were ready to experience the study conditions.

If participants were assigned to one of the tutorial conditions, they first experienced the respective tutorial. Due to their conceptual differences, both tutorials differ in length. For the *T&E* condition, the tutorial took an average of 63.78 seconds of free exploration time, while the *GHOST* condition featured 33.80 seconds of predetermined, animated movements. Afterwards, participants in all three conditions played the game for five minutes (decided based on previous VR exergame studies [9, 44, 48, 66]). During the gameplay, we recorded their heart rate and game performance metrics. In all conditions, the gameplay was completely identical, with the spawned blocks and their spawn positions.

After completing the game, participants filled out the post-game questionnaires. If they had been assigned to one of the tutorial conditions (i.e., *T&E* or *GHOST*), they additionally evaluated the usefulness of the tutorial. Finally, they provided optional feedback using the open-ended question. The total duration of the study was approximately 30 minutes per participant. If applicable, participants received credit, which is required for their degree program to collect. The full procedure of the study is illustrated in Figure 4.

5 Analysis & Results

Our study employed a primarily quantitative research design [21] and collected numerical data. However, we also administered a single open-ended question at the end of the study to gather feedback from participants.

Quantitative Analysis. For numerical data, we first conducted Shapiro-Wilk tests to assess normality and Levene’s tests to verify homogeneity of variances for each construct. If these assumptions were met, we performed one-way ANOVA with a single between-factor (conditions) and used unpaired t-tests for pairwise comparisons. If the assumptions were violated, we employed Kruskal-Wallis tests (with conditions as the between-factor) and Wilcoxon rank-sum tests for pairwise comparisons. For metrics that included baseline measurements, such as heart rate and cybersickness, we calculated the difference between post-experience and baseline scores prior to analysis, and then applied the same testing procedures. To analyze the perceived usefulness of the tutorials (i.e., *T&E* and *GHOST*), we employed normality and homogeneity of variance checks, and as a result, we conducted an unpaired t-test. When we conducted post-hoc pairwise comparison tests, we applied the Holm correction and reported adjusted *p*-values in the text.

Qualitative Analysis. We used a content analysis approach [96] to analyze the qualitative data (i.e., an open-ended question). First, the lead author translated the German data into English using DeepL Pro [23] if necessary. Then, they familiarized themselves with the data by reading the text multiple times. Subsequently, the lead author, who has several years of VR and exergame research experience, developed inductive codes (e.g., fun game) and iteratively coded the data. The qualitative findings were summarized through affinity mapping, which involved reiterating, rereading, and grouping quotes and codes, and were then shared with a research team member for discussion. After the discussion, the findings were finalized and reported here. We report the quotes based on the participant index and the condition, indicated as a subscript (e.g., $P - 1_{BASE}$).

5.1 Questionnaires

We observed no significant differences in cybersickness symptoms, embodiment, presence, physical activity enjoyment, and some of the player experience as well as workload ratings. Please refer to Table 1 for the full statistics, including test results, *p*-values, and effect sizes.

We found a significant difference between conditions on participants’ IMI interest/enjoyment (i.e., intrinsic motivation) scores ($H(2)=7.696$, $p=0.021$, $\eta^2_{[H]}=0.100$). The post-hoc tests revealed a significant difference only between *BASE* and *GHOST* ($W=93.0$, $p=0.012$). However, no significant differences were observed between *BASE* and *T&E* ($W=182.0$, $p=0.635$), nor between *T&E* and *GHOST* ($W=136.5$, $p=0.175$, see Figure 6).

We observed significant differences across the conditions in the following subcategories of PXI: meaning ($F(2,57)=5.773$, $p=0.005$, $\eta^2_G=0.168$), progress feedback ($F(2,57)=7.777$, $p=0.001$, $\eta^2_G=0.214$), ease of control ($H(2)=22.925$, $p<0.001$, $\eta^2_{[H]}=0.367$), and mastery ($H(2)=6.474$, $p=0.039$, $\eta^2_{[H]}=0.078$). The post-hoc tests showed that participants perceived *GHOST* as more meaningful than both the *BASE* ($t(57)=-3.284$, $p=0.005$) and *T&E* ($t(57)=-2.397$, $p=0.040$) conditions, but no significant difference was found between the *BASE* and *T&E* ($t(57)=-0.888$, $p=0.379$) conditions. Similarly, participants perceived the progress feedback as significantly higher in *GHOST* compared to both *BASE* ($t(57)=-3.777$, $p=0.001$) and *T&E* ($t(57)=-2.872$, $p=0.011$), but no significant difference was observed between

Figure 5: *GHOST* led to higher perceived tutorial usefulness than *T&E*, as well as higher total punch accuracy than both *T&E* and *BASE*.

BASE and *T&E* ($t(57)=-0.905$, $p=0.369$) in terms of the progress feedback. Participants reported significantly higher ease of control in the *GHOST* condition compared to all conditions (*BASE*: $W=22.5$, $p<0.001$ and *T&E*: $W=117.0$, $p=0.036$), but *T&E* also led to significantly higher ease of control ratings compared to *BASE*, $W=112.5$, $p=0.036$. For mastery, after post-hoc Holm correction, the significant differences between the conditions disappeared (*BASE* vs. *T&E*: $W=177.5$, $p=0.549$, *BASE* vs. *GHOST*: $W=118.0$, $p=0.078$, *T&E* vs. *GHOST*: $W=123.5$, $p=0.078$, see Figure 6).

Only the NASA-TLX frustration scores ($H(2)=12.613$, $p=0.002$, $\eta^2_{[H]}=0.186$) showed a significant difference among the NASA-TLX subcategories (see Table 1). The post-hoc pairwise comparison tests revealed significant differences between *BASE* and *T&E* ($W=298.5$, $p=0.015$) and between *BASE* and *GHOST* ($W=322.5$, $p=0.003$) on NASA-TLX frustration ratings, while *T&E* and *GHOST* showed no significant difference ($W=223.0$, $p=0.535$, see Figure 6).

We found a significant difference between the tutorials (*T&E* and *GHOST*) in their usefulness ratings ($W=120.5$, $p=0.032$, $r=0.342$), with the *GHOST* condition perceived as more useful (see Figure 5).

5.2 Objective Metrics

We found a significant effect of the conditions on participants’ accuracy of punching the blocks ($H(2)=23.595$, $p<0.001$, $\eta^2_{[H]}=0.379$). The post-hoc tests revealed that *GHOST* condition led to a higher level of accuracy compared to all conditions, *BASE*: $W=357$, $p<0.001$, and *T&E*: $W=295$, $p=0.009$. Similarly, in *T&E*, participants achieved significantly higher accuracy compared to *BASE*: $W=325$, $p=0.001$ (see Figure 5). However, we did not observe significant differences across the conditions regarding physical activity or heart rate difference (see Table 1 for full statistics).

5.3 Qualitative Feedback

We received optional qualitative feedback from only 29 participants. Thirteen participants reported that they found *BoxPunchVR* enjoyable, regardless of the conditions: “I had a lot of fun playing the game!”- $P - 12_{T&E}$. However, a few participants experienced challenges in recalling the correct punching directions for the blocks in the gameplay: “While playing the game it was sometimes hard to remember which symbol stands for which actions”- $P - 48_{BASE}$.

Table 1: Median, interquartile range, and statistical test values of the used metrics in the study. Significance is marked with *.

QUESTIONNAIRES	BASE <i>Mdn (IQR)</i>	T&E <i>Mdn (IQR)</i>	GHOST <i>Mdn (IQR)</i>	TEST	P VALUE	EFFECT SIZE
<i>VEQ</i>						
Acceptance	4.63 (1.13)	4.75 (1.38)	5.50 (0.94)	$H(2)=4.761$	0.092	$\eta^2_{[H]} = 0.048$
Control	6.13 (1.00)	6.25 (1.00)	6.25 (0.50)	$H(2)=1.730$	0.421	$\eta^2_{[H]} = -0.005$
<i>IPQ</i>						
Presence	2.00 (1.00)	2.00 (1.00)	2.00 (1.00)	$H(2)=0.922$	0.631	$\eta^2_{[H]} = -0.019$
Spatial Presence	1.40 (0.80)	1.30 (0.90)	1.80 (0.50)	$H(2)=4.633$	0.099	$\eta^2_{[H]} = 0.046$
Involvement	1.25 (1.56)	1.25 (1.75)	1.38 (1.31)	$F(2,57)=0.307$	0.737	$\eta^2_G = 0.011$
Exp. Realism	-0.63 (1.31)	-0.63 (1.63)	-0.63 (1.13)	$F(2,57)=0.713$	0.340	$\eta^2_G = 0.012$
<i>NASA-TLX</i>						
Mental Demand	37.50 (31.25)	30.00 (28.75)	25.00 (38.75)	$H(2)=0.849$	0.654	$\eta^2_{[H]} = -0.020$
Physical Demand	25.00 (16.25)	17.50 (31.25)	25.00 (36.25)	$H(2)=1.717$	0.424	$\eta^2_{[H]} = -0.005$
Temporal Demand	25.00 (15.00)	42.50 (38.75)	45.00 (27.50)	$H(2)=5.138$	0.077	$\eta^2_{[H]} = 0.055$
Performance	70.00 (37.50)	67.50 (23.75)	80.00 (26.25)	$H(2)=3.201$	0.202	$\eta^2_{[H]} = 0.021$
Effort	35.00 (25.00)	32.50 (27.50)	35.00 (45.00)	$H(2)=1.216$	0.545	$\eta^2_{[H]} = -0.014$
Frustration	27.50 (36.25)	7.50 (27.50)	7.50 (20.00)	$H(2)=12.613$	0.002	** $\eta^2_{[H]} = 0.186$
<i>PXI</i>						
Meaning	-1.00 (1.83)	0.00 (1.67)	1.00 (1.33)	$F(2,57)=5.773$	0.005	** $\eta^2_G = 0.168$
Curiosity	0.67 (1.33)	1.00 (2.25)	1.17 (1.67)	$F(2,57)=0.221$	0.802	$\eta^2_G = 0.008$
Mastery	1.50 (1.67)	1.17 (1.33)	1.83 (1.00)	$H(2)=6.474$	0.039	* $\eta^2_{[H]} = 0.078$
Autonomy	-1.00 (2.08)	-0.50 (1.83)	0.50 (2.33)	$H(2)=1.644$	0.440	$\eta^2_{[H]} = -0.006$
Immersion	1.33 (1.33)	1.83 (1.75)	1.67 (1.00)	$F(2,57)=1.150$	0.324	$\eta^2_G = 0.039$
Progress Feedback	-0.67 (1.50)	0.00 (2.75)	1.17 (1.33)	$F(2,57)=7.777$	0.001	** $\eta^2_G = 0.214$
Audiovisual Appeal	1.33 (1.00)	0.83 (2.17)	1.67 (1.08)	$H(2)=2.147$	0.342	$\eta^2_{[H]} = 0.003$
Challenge	1.17 (1.17)	1.33 (2.00)	1.33 (1.42)	$H(2)=0.895$	0.639	$\eta^2_{[H]} = -0.019$
Ease of Control	1.00 (1.25)	1.83 (1.75)	2.50 (1.00)	$H(2)=22.925$	<0.001	*** $\eta^2_{[H]} = 0.367$
Clarity of Goals	2.00 (1.33)	2.00 (1.08)	2.33 (1.08)	$H(2)=2.091$	0.352	$\eta^2_{[H]} = 0.002$
<i>SSQ</i>						
Diff. Nausea	0.00 (9.54)	0.00 (2.38)	0.00 (9.54)	$H(2)=0.934$	0.627	$\eta^2_{[H]} = -0.019$
Diff. Oculomotor	0.00 (7.58)	0.00 (9.48)	0.00 (1.90)	$H(2)=0.476$	0.788	$\eta^2_{[H]} = -0.027$
Diff. Disorientation	0.00 (13.92)	0.00 (0.00)	0.00 (0.00)	$H(2)=3.352$	0.197	$\eta^2_{[H]} = 0.022$
Diff. Total	0.00 (5.61)	0.00 (8.41)	0.00 (1.87)	$H(2)=0.000$	1.000	$\eta^2_{[H]} = -0.035$
<i>Others</i>						
IMI Int./Enj.	5.50 (1.07)	5.57 (2.04)	6.21 (0.82)	$H(2)=7.696$	0.021	* $\eta^2_{[H]} = 0.100$
PACES-S	4.00 (0.69)	4.13 (1.44)	4.50 (1.00)	$H(2)=1.776$	0.411	$\eta^2_{[H]} = -0.004$
Tut. Usefulness	— (—)	4.25 (3.13)	6.00 (3.00)	$W=120.5$	0.032	* $r = 0.342$
<i>Objective Metrics</i>						
Total Accuracy	0.74 (0.15)	0.85 (0.07)	0.92 (0.10)	$H(2)=23.595$	<0.001	*** $\eta^2_{[H]} = 0.379$
Physical Activity	263.70 (102.90)	306.53 (116.17)	291.76 (104.14)	$F(2,57)=0.850$	0.433	$\eta^2_G = 0.029$
Heart Rate Diff.	17.58 (15.74)	21.86 (8.72)	21.19 (18.57)	$H(2)=1.155$	0.561	$\eta^2_{[H]} = -0.015$

Six participants who had the *BASE* condition explicitly mentioned unclarity they experienced, indicating difficulties in understanding the game's objective: "At first I did not notice my points and then I already had so many minus points"- $P - 3_{BASE}$ and "I was missing instructions on how to hit which cube/symbol"- $P - 10_{BASE}$. However, for some of these participants, these unclarity were only

temporary and diminished after a while: "Only at the beginning I was confused, about how I should push the boxes"- $P - 24_{BASE}$. Similarly, a few participants who experienced the *T&E* reported feelings of confusion and expressed a desire for more guidance: "Some explanation in form of a text would have helped to know which punches to throw"- $P - 37_{T&E}$. Interestingly, two participants who experienced

Figure 6: *GHOST* (red) was perceived as more meaningful, and providing more progress feedback and ease of control than all other conditions. Although both *GHOST* (red) and *T&E* (orange) led to significantly less frustration than *BASE* (blue), only *GHOST* (red) was found to be more motivating.

the *GHOST* required some time to understand the tutorial: “I was a little unprepared for the tutorial and didn’t know what to pay attention to first, but then the tutorial was very well made and gave me enough time to understand the mechanics of the game”-P – 8_{GHOST}.

6 Discussion

In our study, we designed tutorials for VR exergames based on a theory-driven approach. Specifically, we developed two tutorial modes, one emphasizing self-model learning [4, 5, 18] (*GHOST*) and the other focusing on trial-and-error learning [82, 91] (*T&E*), along with a control condition that did not include a tutorial (*BASE*). Based on our findings, we address our research questions in the discussion. Finally, we outline implications for the design and future research of VR exergame tutorials.

6.1 Tutorials are important for VR exergames.

Although there are successful games without tutorials (e.g., *Pac-Man* [69]), research shows that providing tutorials in complex video games can increase both players’ playtime and in-game performance [2]. However, this result is based on a study with puzzle games and has not been observed in simple games [2]. Since Kao et al. [42] emphasize the importance of genre-specific requirements in the tutorial design of VR games, **RQ1** explored if tutorials are beneficial in VR exergames. Our findings indicate that both tutorial modes (i.e., *T&E* and *GHOST*) result in significantly better punch accuracy compared to playing without a tutorial. The qualitative feedback supports this outcome, as players who did not receive a tutorial reported confusion about the game’s goals and interactions. This finding is remarkable given the, compared to other commercial games, still simpler game design of *BoxPunchVR*. It suggests that tutorials can help players in VR exergames better understand the game mechanics and perform actions more accurately. In terms of player workload, we observed a similar trend: Tutorials significantly reduced player frustration during gameplay. Accordingly, our results suggest that tutorials can play an important role in teaching game mechanics in VR exergames, as supported by improved player performance. By reducing frustration, tutorials may

also encourage players to engage with VR exergames for longer periods and return for repeated play sessions. However, we note that ideally, all games should be intuitive and require no tutorial for players to use them. Nonetheless, in the context of VR exergames, it might be beneficial for players to understand the correct execution of movements through tutorials (cf. [48]), not only to maximize the benefits of the exercise but also to reduce the risk of injuries.

6.2 The self-model tutorial does not significantly diminish embodiment compared to other conditions.

Previous research has shown that users can experience a sense of virtual body ownership even when embodying avatars of a different gender [86] or non-humanoid forms [55, 56]. In VR exergame studies, ghost avatars of the player-selves have been used to visualize previous or future performances and promote self-competition [6, 66, 83]. However, to our knowledge, previous studies have not examined the effect of temporarily losing and then regaining control over one’s virtual avatar. Our results, with regards to **RQ2**, indicate that a short-term loss in agency in the *GHOST* condition does not significantly diminish feelings of virtual body acceptance or agency compared to *T&E*. These findings suggest that the sense of embodiment in VR may withstand brief interruptions in agency without negatively affecting users’ experience. In practical terms, this indicates that designers of VR exergames can consider implementing such transitions, guided demonstrations, or other temporary shifts in avatar control without necessarily reducing users’ sense of embodiment (see [19]) for multi-character transition techniques in VR), although further research is needed to understand how different durations or contexts of agency interruption may affect user experiences.

6.3 The self-model tutorial supports accuracy and motivation but does not significantly affect physical activity.

In our exploratory study, we drew on social learning theory [4, 5], with a particular focus on self-model learning, and trial-and-error

theory [82, 91] to investigate how tutorials can influence players' performance and experience (RQ2). Our results offer a nuanced perspective, revealing which specific aspects of player experience and performance are influenced by different tutorial approaches.

Notably, our novel tutorial (*GHOST*) led to higher punching accuracy compared to the traditional trial-and-error method (*T&E*). However, while *GHOST* increased player motivation relative to not receiving any tutorial, this motivational benefit was not observed when comparing *T&E* to *BASE*. Additionally, the increased motivation in the *GHOST* condition did not translate into a significantly greater amount of movement. While it is generally expected that higher motivation leads to increased movement (i.e., more physical activity), in our scenario, greater motivation may have contributed to improved accuracy rather than resulting in more erratic or excessive movements. Since fast, full-body movements can pose injury risks and correct execution is especially important in rehabilitative contexts, these accuracy improvements could open future opportunities for VR exergames involving rapid, full-body movements (e.g., [20]) as well as for therapy-focused exergames (e.g., [16]). Therefore, we do not regard the absence of activity-related differences as a sign of the ineffectiveness of our tutorials. Instead, we focus on their effect on movement accuracy. Although the *T&E* condition already significantly improved punching accuracy compared to not receiving any tutorial, the benefit was significantly less than in the *GHOST* condition. While our study suggests that the *T&E* approach can also have benefits, we recommend carefully considering its use in high-injury-risk scenarios, such as jumping in VR [20].

6.4 The trial-and-error tutorial also improves player experience, but self-modeling is even more effective and useful.

Looking at the findings related to player experience (RQ1), we observe that both tutorial modes outperform the no tutorial condition (*BASE*) across several aspects of player experience: Players perceived the game as significantly more meaningful and providing greater ease of control when being onboarded with either type of tutorial. Notably, the effects of the *GHOST* tutorial were even more pronounced than those of the *T&E* tutorial (answering RQ2). Players experienced significantly higher progress feedback and reported greater ease of control with the *GHOST* condition. This is further supported by participant ratings of usefulness, with *GHOST* being rated significantly more useful than *T&E*. Qualitative feedback also reflected this positive impression, with one participant noting that “the tutorial was very well made and gave me [players] enough time to understand the mechanics of the game”-P - 8_{GHOST}.

Providing ease of control is particularly important in VR exergames, as player actions are closely tied to physical movement and accurate interaction with the virtual environment. Looking past our target sample, teaching how to interact with the game is especially important for older adults who often feel frustrated from exergames' overly complex or fast-paced gameplay [7, 36]. Likewise, the significantly higher progress feedback reported for *GHOST* suggests that the self-model approach enabled players to effectively mirror the presented movements and use their formed mental model to continuously evaluate their own performance during the game. Since repeatedly failing levels is a major reason for

players to quit exergames [73], we hope that the improved reflection and adaptation of own skills can help prevent this outcome. All in all, our study indicates the benefits of the observational learning method for teaching bodily movements in playful contexts.

6.5 Implications for Design and Future Research

Based on our findings and theoretical framing, we propose implications for future design and research of VR exergame tutorials.

6.5.1 Design for transitional embodiment. In our exploratory study, we designed *GHOST* to introduce a novel concept we refer to as *transitional embodiment*, where players shift between active control and passive observation of their own avatar. Looking beyond our study, future work could explore the design space of tutorials that use transitional embodiment to gradually scaffold agency—starting with observation, then partial control, and finally full autonomy. In particular, future tutorial research could look into this design space to deepen our understanding of how such designs can influence learning, performance, and experience outcomes. However, we also recognize that the user's wish for autonomy and the specific context in which transitional embodiment is applied can greatly affect the experience. For example, observation and partial control switches might be particularly beneficial in learning or rehabilitation scenarios, where an expert model helps to correct actions of the learner. Similar to the concept of transitional embodiment, prior research has explored *virtual co-embodiment* in which multiple parties share control of an avatar [29]. Kodama et al. [52]'s results show that virtual co-embodiment between learner and teacher can enhance motor learning efficiency compared to learning alone or completing the task by sharing the teacher's perspective. In contrast, implementing shared control within games may lead to player frustration or challenges due to differing skill dynamics among players [103]. However, it could also encourage more social interaction or provide experiential benefits [88, 89, 103]. These context-dependent factors highlight the need for further research on how to best tailor transitional and partial embodiment in different VR applications.

6.5.2 Design player-sensitive tutorials. Looking primarily at the quantitative findings of our exploratory study, we observe that while *GHOST* offers clear advantages, such as improved punch accuracy, we do not see these benefits across all measured constructs. For example, *GHOST* did not lead to significantly less frustration compared to *T&E*. These results indicate that a one-size-fits-all approach is unlikely to address the diverse needs and characteristics of players. Our qualitative results also support this by suggesting that some players experienced confusion or wished for more guidance. Drawing inspiration from context-sensitive tutorials, where instructions are provided precisely when players encounter specific game mechanics [2, 31], we propose the development of *player-sensitive tutorials* that respond to real-time challenges matching with players' learning styles in VR exergames. In this approach, VR exergames can continuously monitor player performance to detect moments when a player encounters difficulty with particular movements. Similar to performance coaching [39] and just-in-time suggestions [17], the tutorial could then automatically provide targeted support, such as additional self-model demonstrations. By

adapting tutorials to individual abilities and preferences, player-sensitive tutorials could make VR exergames more engaging and more effective for a broader range of users.

6.5.3 Explore other types of tutorial designs based on other learning theories. Our approach to designing tutorials was informed by the classification of White [97] and shaped by two learning theories commonly applied in sports and educational contexts to understand behavioral learning: social learning theory [4, 5] and trial-and-error theory [82, 91]. While our study illustrates an example of how to integrate these theories into VR exergame research, we do not claim that our approach fully encompasses all aspects of these theories. For instance, both theories identify subcomponents that influence how people acquire new behaviors. According to Bandura [4], if individuals are not attentive to the stimulus, learning cannot begin. In our tutorial designs, we incorporated core principles from these theories, such as performing actions and learning through consequences, or observing and imitating one's own actions, but a thorough exploration of their underlying subcomponents and influencing factors remains as future research directions. Similarly, although we focused on two theories in our exploratory study, there is a wide range of learning theories (see [82]) that can be considered and drawn upon for designing tutorials in VR exergames.

6.6 Limitations

In our study, we assessed players' punch accuracy, which served as an indicator of both learning and performance. While additional metrics, such as detailed movement analysis, could offer more comprehensive insights into punch execution, accurately capturing these explosive and forceful actions would necessitate more sophisticated hardware and software solutions. However, these metrics could also help researchers understand how to achieve safer, more precise execution of movements using different tutorial approaches. Nevertheless, safety outcomes were not measured in our study, leaving a gap for future research.

As with all HCI artifact-based studies, our results are influenced by the specific design of our applications. To enhance external validity and the generalizability of our findings, we designed a VR exergame that incorporates the most commonly used task (i.e., target-based tasks) identified in immersive exergame research [43] and drew inspiration from boxing-themed commercial VR exergames such as *FitXR* and *BlackBox VR* [28, 95]. Yet, we also acknowledge that in different task-focused VR exergames, such as those involving continuous or full-body movements, alternative tutorial approaches may offer distinct advantages. For example, meditation-based VR exergames might benefit more from audio-based tutorials rather than those primarily designed around visual components.

Regarding generalizability, our study recruited young and middle-aged adults who could safely perform upper body movements while standing. However, other user groups, such as older adults and children, could also benefit from the physical activity offered by VR exergames. While our results may provide some guidance for designing VR exergame tutorials for these populations, it is essential to consider their differing needs and experiences (e.g., [44, 58]). For instance, *GHOST* might cause irritation among older adults due to experiencing a temporary loss of agency with a ghost

avatar, as they may be less familiar with novel technologies and concepts.

In our study, we adopted a ghost avatar representation in our design, reflecting its frequent use in VR exergame research [66, 83] as a self-representation concept. However, alternative avatar representations are possible and offer promising directions for future research to better understand the nuanced interactions between avatar design, the VR exergame genre, and learning contexts. For example, Koulouris et al. [54] found that realistic avatar representation can improve performance in VR exergames, while Fitton et al. [27] showed that demonstrator-learner similarity does not significantly affect fine motor skill learning.

Finally, we note that, while our results offer empirical insights into learning outcomes based on performance metrics, they are derived from short-term gameplay. Consequently, learning retention and long-term transfer remain areas for future investigation.

7 Conclusion

VR exergames are gaining increasing attention in both research and the commercial market. However, there is still limited understanding of whether and which types of tutorials support player experience and performance in these games. In our work, we drew on learning theories and sports sciences to develop and evaluate two types of tutorials: (i) a trial-and-error tutorial and (ii) a novel self-model tutorial. In the self-model tutorial, players temporarily lose the control of their avatar and observe a ghost version of themselves performing the tutorial, whereas in the trial-and-error tutorial, players learn by actively experimenting and experiencing the consequences of their actions. Our between-participants study with 60 participants showed that the self-model tutorial not only improved player performance, but also offered greater ease of control and higher perceived progress feedback compared to the trial-and-error approach. Based on these findings, we presented three implications: We highlighted the potential of transitional embodiment, encouraged the exploration of player-sensitive tutorials, and suggested further investigation of tutorial designs grounded in additional learning theories.

Acknowledgments

We thank the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program (PRESENCE project, 101135025), the MSCA Staff Exchanges project PLACES (101086206), the Federal Ministry of Research, Technology, and Space (Rescue-Mate project, 13N15596 and 13N15597), and the German Research Foundation (EYERES project, LA 952/11) for supporting this research.

References

- [1] Vero Vanden Abeele, Katta Spiel, Lennart Nacke, Daniel Johnson, and Kathrin Gerling. 2020. Development and validation of the player experience inventory: A scale to measure player experiences at the level of functional and psychosocial consequences. *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies* 135 (2020), 102370. doi:10.1016/j.ijhcs.2019.102370
- [2] Erik Andersen, Eleanor O'Rourke, Yun-En Liu, Rich Snider, Jeff Lowdermilk, David Truong, Seth Cooper, and Zoran Popovic. 2012. The impact of tutorials on games of varying complexity. In *Proceedings of the SIGCHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (Austin, Texas, USA) (CHI '12). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 59–68. doi:10.1145/2207676.2207687
- [3] Abdul Syafiq Bahrin, Mohd Shahrizal Sunar, and Hadafi Fitri Mohd Latip. 2023. Self-competition Virtual Reality Cycling for Enhanced Motivation: Interactive

- Feedforward Adjustments. In *International Conference on Innovation and Technology in Sports*. Springer, 99–105. doi:10.1007/978-981-97-3741-3_11
- [4] Albert Bandura. 1977. *Social learning theory*. Vol. 1. Prentice hall Englewood Cliffs, NJ.
- [5] Albert Bandura et al. 1986. Social foundations of thought and action. *Englewood Cliffs, NJ* 1986, 23-28 (1986), 2.
- [6] Soumya C. Barathi, Daniel J. Finnegan, Matthew Farrow, Alexander Whaley, Pippa Heath, Jude Buckley, Peter W. Dowrick, Burkhard C. Wuensche, James L. J. Bilzon, Eamonn O'Neill, and Christof Lutteroth. 2018. Interactive Feedforward for Improving Performance and Maintaining Intrinsic Motivation in VR Exergaming. In *Proceedings of the 2018 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (Montreal QC, Canada) (CHI '18). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 1–14. doi:10.1145/3173574.3173982
- [7] Laura H Barg-Walkow, Christina N Harrington, Tracy L Mitzner, Jordan Q Hartley, and Wendy A Rogers. 2017. Understanding older adults' perceptions of and attitudes towards exergames. *Gerontechnology: international journal on the fundamental aspects of technology to serve the ageing society* 16, 2 (2017), 81.
- [8] Felix Born, Sophie Abramowski, and Maic Masuch. 2019. Exergaming in VR: The Impact of Immersive Embodiment on Motivation, Performance, and Perceived Exertion. In *2019 11th International Conference on Virtual Worlds and Games for Serious Applications (VS-Games)*. IEEE, 1–8. doi:10.1109/VS-Games.2019.8864579
- [9] Felix Born, Adrian Rygula, and Maic Masuch. 2021. Motivating Players to Perform an Optional Strenuous Activity in a Virtual Reality Exergame Using Virtual Performance Augmentation. *Proc. ACM Hum.-Comput. Interact.* 5, CHI PLAY, Article 225 (oct 2021), 21 pages. doi:10.1145/3474652
- [10] Giovanni Buccino, Stefan Vogt, Afra Ritzl, Gereon R Fink, Karl Zilles, Hans-Joachim Freund, and Giacomo Rizzolatti. 2004. Neural circuits underlying imitation learning of hand actions: an event-related fMRI study. *Neuron* 42, 2 (2004), 323–334. doi:10.1016/S0896-6273(04)00181-3
- [11] Kelly Caine. 2016. Local Standards for Sample Size at CHI. In *Proceedings of the 2016 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (San Jose, California, USA) (CHI '16). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 981–992. doi:10.1145/2858036.2858498
- [12] Alberto Cannavò, Filippo Gabriele Praticò, Giuseppe Ministeri, and Fabrizio Lamberti. 2018. A Movement Analysis System based on Immersive Virtual Reality and Wearable Technology for Sport Training. In *Proceedings of the 4th International Conference on Virtual Reality (Hong Kong, Hong Kong) (ICVR 2018)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 26–31. doi:10.1145/3198910.3198917
- [13] Edwige Chauvergne, Martin Hachet, and Arnaud Prouzeau. 2023. User Onboarding in Virtual Reality: An Investigation of Current Practices. In *Proceedings of the 2023 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (Hamburg, Germany) (CHI '23). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, Article 711, 15 pages. doi:10.1145/3544548.3581211
- [14] Boyuan Chen, Xinan Yan, Xuning Hu, Dominic Kao, and Hai-Ning Liang. 2024. Impact of Tutorial Modes with Different Time Flow Rates in Virtual Reality Games. *Proc. ACM Comput. Graph. Interact. Tech.* 7, 1, Article 6 (May 2024), 19 pages. doi:10.1145/3651296
- [15] Cheng Chen, Susanne Weyland, Julian Fritsch, Alexander Woll, Claudia Niessner, Alexander Burchartz, Steffen C. E. Schmidt, and Darko Jekauc. 2021. A Short Version of the Physical Activity Enjoyment Scale: Development and Psychometric Properties. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 18, 21 (2021), 15 pages. doi:10.3390/ijerph182111035
- [16] Maria Chiu, Elina Toichilnikova, and Casper Hartevelde. 2024. From Novelty to Clinical Practice: Exploring VR Exergames with Physical Therapists. *Proc. ACM Hum.-Comput. Interact.* 8, CHI PLAY, Article 303 (Oct. 2024), 29 pages. doi:10.1145/3677068
- [17] Lydia Choong, Sebastian Cmentowski, Eugene Kukshinov, Joseph Tu, and Lennart E. Nacke. 2025. Support Autonomy: Exploring Player Perspectives on AI-Supported Onboarding in Video Games. In *Proceedings of the 2025 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI '25)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, Article 464, 17 pages. doi:10.1145/3706598.3713576
- [18] Shannon E. Clark and Diane M. Ste-Marie. 2007. The impact of self-as-a-model interventions on children's self-regulation of learning and swimming performance. *Journal of Sports Sciences* 25, 5 (2007), 577–586. doi:10.1080/02640410600947090
- [19] Sebastian Cmentowski, Sukran Karaosmanoglu, Fabian Kivelitz, Frank Steinicke, and Jens Krüger. 2023. A Matter of Perspective: Designing Immersive Character Transitions for Virtual Reality Games. *Proc. ACM Hum.-Comput. Interact.* 7, CHI PLAY, Article 377 (Oct. 2023), 31 pages. doi:10.1145/3611023
- [20] Sebastian Cmentowski, Sukran Karaosmanoglu, Lennart E. Nacke, Frank Steinicke, and Jens Harald Krüger. 2023. Never Skip Leg Day Again: Training the Lower Body with Vertical Jumps in a Virtual Reality Exergame. In *Proceedings of the 2023 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (Hamburg, Germany) (CHI '23). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, Article 786, 18 pages. doi:10.1145/3544548.3580973
- [21] John W Creswell. 2017. *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*. Sage publications.
- [22] Daniel J. Cucher, Melissa S. Kovacs, Clarence E. Clark, and Charles K.P. Hu. 2023. Virtual reality consumer product injuries: An analysis of national emergency department data. *Injury* 54, 5 (2023), 1396–1399. doi:10.1016/j.injury.2023.01.030
- [23] DeepL SE. 2017. DeepL Translator. DeepL Pro version. Cologne, Germany. <https://www.deepl.com/pro?cta=header-pro/>.
- [24] Dennis Dietz, Carl Oechsner, Changkun Ou, Francesco Chiossi, Fabio Sarto, Sven Mayer, and Andreas Butz. 2022. Walk This Beam: Impact of Different Balance Assistance Strategies and Height Exposure on Performance and Physiological Arousal in VR. In *Proceedings of the 28th ACM Symposium on Virtual Reality Software and Technology* (Tsukuba, Japan) (VRST '22). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, Article 32, 12 pages. doi:10.1145/3562939.3567818
- [25] Peter W Dowrick. 1999. A review of self modeling and related interventions. *Applied and preventive psychology* 8, 1 (1999), 23–39.
- [26] Matthew Farrow, Christof Lutteroth, Peter C. Rouse, and James L. J. Bilzon. 2019. Virtual-reality exergaming improves performance during high-intensity interval training. *European Journal of Sport Science* 19, 6 (2019), 719–727. doi:10.1080/17461391.2018.1542459
- [27] Isabel Sophie Fitton, Elizabeth Dark, Manoela Milena Oliveira da Silva, Jeremy Dalton, Michael J Proulx, Christopher Clarke, and Christof Lutteroth. 2024. Watch This! Observational Learning in VR Promotes Better Far Transfer than Active Learning for a Fine Psychomotor Task. In *Proceedings of the 2024 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (Honolulu, HI, USA) (CHI '24). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, Article 721, 19 pages. doi:10.1145/3613904.3642550
- [28] FitXR. 2019. *FitXR - Box. HIIT. Dance. Sculpt. Combat.* Game [VR]. FitXR. London, England. Meta Reviews: <https://www.meta.com/experiences/2327205800645550/>.
- [29] Rebecca Fribourg, Nami Ogawa, Ludovic Hoyet, Ferran Argelaguet, Takuji Narumi, Michitaka Hirose, and Anatole Lécuyer. 2021. Virtual Co-Embodiment: Evaluation of the Sense of Agency While Sharing the Control of a Virtual Body Among Two Individuals. *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics* 27, 10 (2021), 4023–4038. doi:10.1109/TVCG.2020.2999197
- [30] Julian Fritsch, Susanne Weyland, Katharina Feil, Alexander Burchartz, Steffen Schmidt, Alexander Woll, Ulrich Strauch, Benjamin Wienke, and Darko Jekauc. 2022. A Study on the Psychometric Properties of the Short Version of the Physical Activity Enjoyment Scale in an Adult Population. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 19, 22 (2022), 11 pages. doi:10.3390/ijerph192215294
- [31] Julian Frommel, Kim Fahlbusch, Julia Brich, and Michael Weber. 2017. The Effects of Context-Sensitive Tutorials in Virtual Reality Games. In *Proceedings of the Annual Symposium on Computer-Human Interaction in Play* (Amsterdam, The Netherlands) (CHI PLAY '17). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 367–375. doi:10.1145/3116595.3116610
- [32] Borko Furht (Ed.). 2008. *Immersive Virtual Reality*. Springer US, Boston, MA, 345–346. doi:10.1007/978-0-387-78414-4_85
- [33] Beat Games. 2019. *Beat Saber*. Game [VR]. Beat Games. Los Angeles, CA, USA. <https://beatsaber.com/>. Steam Reviews: https://store.steampowered.com/app/620980/Beat_Saber/. Accessed: 16.06.2023.
- [34] Mar González-Franco, Tabitha C Peck, Antoni Rodríguez-Fornells, and Mel Slater. 2014. A threat to a virtual hand elicits motor cortex activation. *Experimental brain research* 232, 3 (2014), 875–887. doi:10.1007/s00221-013-3800-1
- [35] Yankun Han, Syed Kamaruzaman Bin Syed Ali, and Lifu Ji. 2022. Use of Observational Learning to Promote Motor Skill Learning in Physical Education: A Systematic Review. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 19, 16 (2022). doi:10.3390/ijerph191610109
- [36] Christina N. Harrington, Jordan Q. Hartley, Tracy L. Mitzner, and Wendy A. Rogers. 2015. Assessing Older Adults' Usability Challenges Using Kinect-Based Exergames. In *Human Aspects of IT for the Aged Population. Design for Everyday Life*, Jia Zhou and Gavriel Salvendy (Eds.). Springer International Publishing, Cham, 488–499.
- [37] Sandra G. Hart. 2006. Nasa-Task Load Index (NASA-TLX); 20 Years Later. *Proceedings of the Human Factors and Ergonomics Society Annual Meeting* 50, 9 (2006), 904–908. doi:10.1177/154193120605000909
- [38] Anne Hösche. 2018. *Simulator Sickness in Fahrsimulationsumgebungen-drei Studien zu Human Factors*. Ph.D. Dissertation. Technische Universität Ilmenau. https://www.db-thueringen.de/receive/dbt_mods_00037865
- [39] Rob Houser and Scott DeLoach. 1998. Learning from games: Seven principles of effective design. *Technical communication* 45, 3 (1998), 319–329.
- [40] Christos Ioannou, Patrick Archard, Eamonn O'Neill, and Christof Lutteroth. 2019. Virtual Performance Augmentation in an Immersive Jump & Run Exergame. In *Proceedings of the 2019 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (Glasgow, Scotland Uk) (CHI '19). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 1–15. doi:10.1145/3290605.3300388
- [41] Robert S. P. Jones, Linda Clare, Conor MacPartlin, and Olivia Murphy. 2010. The Effectiveness of Trial-and-Error and Errorless Learning in Promoting the Transfer of Training. *European Journal of Behavior Analysis* 11, 1 (2010), 29–36. doi:10.1080/15021149.2010.11434332

- [42] Dominic Kao, Alejandra J. Magana, and Christos Mousas. 2021. Evaluating Tutorial-Based Instructions for Controllers in Virtual Reality Games. *Proc. ACM Hum.-Comput. Interact.* 5, CHI PLAY, Article 234 (Oct. 2021), 28 pages. doi:10.1145/3474661
- [43] Sukran Karaosmanoglu, Sebastian Cmentowski, Lennart E. Nacke, and Frank Steinicke. 2024. Born to Run, Programmed to Play: Mapping the Extended Reality Exergames Landscape. In *Proceedings of the 2024 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (Honolulu, HI, USA) (CHI '24). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 28 pages. doi:10.1145/3613904.3642124
- [44] Sukran Karaosmanoglu, Sebastian Cmentowski, Lennart E. Nacke, and Frank Steinicke. 2025. ExerCube vs. Virtual Reality: A Comparative Study of Exergame Technologies for Older Adults. *Proc. ACM Hum.-Comput. Interact.* 9, 6, Article GAMES008 (Oct. 2025), 24 pages. doi:10.1145/3748603
- [45] Sukran Karaosmanoglu, Lucie Kruse, Sebastian Rings, and Frank Steinicke. 2022. Canoe VR: An Immersive Exergame to Support Cognitive and Physical Exercises of Older Adults. In *Extended Abstracts of the 2022 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (New Orleans, LA, USA) (CHI EA '22). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, Article 342, 7 pages. doi:10.1145/3491101.3519736
- [46] Sukran Karaosmanoglu, Sebastian Rings, Lucie Kruse, Christian Stein, and Frank Steinicke. 2021. Lessons Learned from a Human-Centered Design of an Immersive Exergame for People with Dementia. *Proc. ACM Hum.-Comput. Interact.* 5, CHI PLAY, Article 252 (oct 2021), 27 pages. doi:10.1145/3474679
- [47] Sukran Karaosmanoglu, Katja Rogers, Dennis Wolf, Enrico Rukzio, Frank Steinicke, and Lennart E. Nacke. 2021. Feels like Team Spirit: Biometric and Strategic Interdependence in Asymmetric Multiplayer VR Games. In *Proceedings of the 2021 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (Yokohama, Japan) (CHI '21). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, Article 443, 15 pages. doi:10.1145/3411764.3445492
- [48] Sukran Karaosmanoglu, Moritz Wegner, Sebastian Cmentowski, and Frank Steinicke. 2024. Move, React, Repeat! The Role of Continuous Cues in Immersive Exergames. *Proc. ACM Hum.-Comput. Interact.* 8, CHI PLAY, Article 326 (Oct. 2024), 23 pages. doi:10.1145/3677091
- [49] Robert S. Kennedy, Norman E. Lane, Kevin S. Berbaum, and Michael G. Lilienthal. 1993. Simulator Sickness Questionnaire: An Enhanced Method for Quantifying Simulator Sickness. *The International Journal of Aviation Psychology* 3, 3 (1993), 203–220. doi:10.1207/s15327108ijap0303_3
- [50] Konstantina Kilteni, Raphaela Groten, and Mel Slater. 2012. The Sense of Embodiment in Virtual Reality. *Presence: Teleoperators and Virtual Environments* 21, 4 (11 2012), 373–387. doi:10.1162/PRES_a_00124
- [51] Konstantina Kilteni, Jean-Marie Normand, Maria V. Sanchez-Vives, and Mel Slater. 2012. Extending Body Space in Immersive Virtual Reality: A Very Long Arm Illusion. *PLOS ONE* 7, 7 (07 2012), 1–15. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0040867
- [52] Daiki Kodama, Takato Mizuhō, Yuji Hatada, Takuji Narumi, and Michitaka Hirose. 2023. Effects of Collaborative Training Using Virtual Co-embodiment on Motor Skill Learning. *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics* 29, 5 (2023), 2304–2314. doi:10.1109/TVCG.2023.3247112
- [53] Tanja Kojić, Lan Thao Nguyen, and Jan-Niklas Voigt-Antons. 2019. Impact of Constant Visual Biofeedback on User Experience in Virtual Reality Exergames. In *2019 IEEE International Symposium on Multimedia (ISM)*. 307–3073. doi:10.1109/ISM46123.2019.00068
- [54] Jordan Koulouris, Zoe Jeffery, James Best, Eamonn O'Neill, and Christof Lutteroth. 2020. Me vs. Super(wo)man: Effects of Customization and Identification in a VR Exergame. In *Proceedings of the 2020 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (Honolulu, HI, USA) (CHI '20). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 1–17. doi:10.1145/3313831.3376661
- [55] Andrey Krekhov, Sebastian Cmentowski, Katharina Emmerich, and Jens Krüger. 2019. Beyond Human: Animals as an Escape from Stereotype Avatars in Virtual Reality Games. In *Proceedings of the Annual Symposium on Computer-Human Interaction in Play* (Barcelona, Spain) (CHI PLAY '19). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 439–451. doi:10.1145/3311350.3347172
- [56] Andrey Krekhov, Sebastian Cmentowski, and Jens Krüger. 2019. The Illusion of Animal Body Ownership and Its Potential for Virtual Reality Games. In *2019 IEEE Conference on Games (CoG)*. 1–8. doi:10.1109/CIG.2019.8848005
- [57] Lucie Kruse, Sukran Karaosmanoglu, Sebastian Rings, Benedikt Ellinger, Daniel Apken, Thandiwe Feziwe Mangana, and Frank Steinicke. 2021. A Long-Term User Study of an Immersive Exergame for Older Adults with Mild Dementia during the COVID-19 Pandemic. In *International Conference on Artificial Reality and Telexistence and Eurographics Symposium on Virtual Environments (ICAT-EGVE '21)*, Jason Orlosky, Dirk Reiners, and Benjamin Weyers (Eds.). The Eurographics Association. doi:10.2312/egve.20211322
- [58] Lucie Kruse, Sukran Karaosmanoglu, Sebastian Rings, and Frank Steinicke. 2022. Evaluating Difficulty Adjustments in a VR Exergame for Younger and Older Adults: Transferabilities and Differences. In *Proceedings of the 2022 ACM Symposium on Spatial User Interaction* (Online, CA, USA) (SUI '22). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, Article 7, 11 pages. doi:10.1145/3565970.3567684
- [59] Yuryeon Lee, Gyeop Kim, Kang Hoon Lee, Jaehyun Park, and Hyun K. Kim. 2024. Comparison of Tutorial Methods in Virtual Reality Games for a Better User Experience. *Applied Sciences* 14, 16 (2024). doi:10.3390/app14167141
- [60] Penelope Lockwood and Ziva Kunda. 1997. Superstars and me: Predicting the impact of role models on the self. *Journal of personality and social psychology* 73, 1 (1997), 91. doi:10.1037/0022-3514.73.1.91
- [61] Richard Magill and David I Anderson. 2010. *Motor learning and control*. McGraw-Hill Publishing New York.
- [62] Antonella Maselli and Mel Slater. 2013. The building blocks of the full body ownership illusion. *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience* Volume 7 - 2013 (2013). doi:10.3389/fnhum.2013.00083
- [63] Penny McCullagh, Barbi Law, and Diane Ste-Marie. 2012. Modeling and Performance. *The Oxford handbook of sport and performance psychology* (2012), 250. doi:10.1093/oxfordhb/9780199731763.013.0013
- [64] Jeremy McDade, Allison Jing, Tasha Stanton, and Ross Smith. 2023. Assessing Superhuman Speed as a Gamified Reward in a Virtual Reality Bike Exergame. In *Extended Abstracts of the 2023 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (Hamburg, Germany) (CHI EA '23). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, Article 41, 8 pages. doi:10.1145/3544549.3585730
- [65] Meta Platforms, Inc. 2023. Meta Quest 3. <https://www.oculus.com/quest-3/> Released: 10 October 2023.
- [66] Alexander Michael and Christof Lutteroth. 2020. Race Yourself: A Longitudinal Exploration of Self-Competition Between Past, Present, and Future Performances in a VR Exergame. In *Proceedings of the 2020 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (Honolulu, HI, USA) (CHI '20). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 1–17. doi:10.1145/3313831.3376256
- [67] Anna Moschny, Petra Platen, Renate Klaußen-Mielke, Ulrike Trampisch, and Timo Hinrichs. 2011. Barriers to physical activity in older adults in Germany: a cross-sectional study. *International Journal of Behavioral Nutrition and Physical Activity* 8, 1 (2011), 1–10. doi:10.1186/1479-5868-8-121
- [68] Florian 'Floyd' Mueller, Darren Edge, Frank Vetere, Martin R. Gibbs, Stefan Agamanolis, Bert Bongers, and Jennifer G. Sheridan. 2011. Designing Sports: A Framework for Exertion Games. In *Proceedings of the SIGCHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (Vancouver, BC, Canada) (CHI '11). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 2651–2660. doi:10.1145/1978942.1979330
- [69] Namco and Bandai Namco Studios. 1980. *Pac-Man*. Game. <https://en.bandainamcoent.eu/games>. Accessed: 10.01.2025.
- [70] Donald A. Norman. 1999. Affordance, conventions, and design. *Interactions* 6, 3 (May 1999), 38–43. doi:10.1145/301153.301168
- [71] Carolyng Pang, Zhiqin Collin Wang, Joanna McGrenere, Rock Leung, Jiamin Dai, and Karyn Moffatt. 2021. Technology Adoption and Learning Preferences for Older Adults: Evolving Perceptions, Ongoing Challenges, and Emerging Design Opportunities. In *Proceedings of the 2021 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (Yokohama, Japan) (CHI '21). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, Article 490, 13 pages. doi:10.1145/3411764.3445702
- [72] Tabitha C. Peck, Sofia Seinfeld, Salvatore M. Aglioti, and Mel Slater. 2013. Putting yourself in the skin of a black avatar reduces implicit racial bias. *Consciousness and Cognition* 22, 3 (2013), 779–787. doi:10.1016/j.concog.2013.04.016
- [73] Peter Rasche, Anna Schломann, and Alexander Mertens. 2017. Who Is Still Playing Pokémon Go? A Web-Based Survey. *JMIR Serious Games* 5, 2 (05 Apr 2017), e7. doi:10.2196/games.7197
- [74] Sébastien Rimbart, Laurent Bougrain, and Stéphanie Fleck. 2020. Learning How to Generate Kinesthetic Motor Imagery Using a BCI-based Learning Environment: a Comparative Study Based on Guided or Trial-and-Error Approaches. In *2020 IEEE International Conference on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics (SMC)*. 2483–2498. doi:10.1109/SMC42975.2020.9283225
- [75] Patrizia Ring, Annika Hemsing, and Maic Masuch. 2025. It's All Fun and Games, Until Someone Gets Hurt: How Game Pace and Player Movement Influence the User Experience in VR. In *Proceedings of the Extended Abstracts of the CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (CHI EA '25). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, Article 362, 7 pages. doi:10.1145/3706599.3720199
- [76] Patrizia Ring and Maic Masuch. 2025. Long-Term Effects of User Expertise and Application Design on Collision Anxiety in VR Games. In *Proceedings of the 2025 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (CHI '25). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, Article 1228, 15 pages. doi:10.1145/3706598.3713970
- [77] Daniel Roth and Marc Erich Latoschik. 2020. Construction of the Virtual Embodiment Questionnaire (VEQ). *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics* 26, 12 (2020), 3546–3556. doi:10.1109/TVCG.2020.3023603
- [78] Richard M Ryan, C Scott Rigby, and Andrew Przybylski. 2006. The motivational pull of video games: A self-determination theory approach. *Motivation and emotion* 30, 4 (2006), 344–360. doi:10.1007/s11031-006-9051-8 The IMI items are available online under this link: <http://selfdeterminationtheory.org/intrinsic-motivation-inventory/>. Accessed: 02.09.2022.

- [79] Anthony Scavarelli and Robert J. Teather. 2017. VR Collide! Comparing Collision-Avoidance Methods Between Co-located Virtual Reality Users. In *Proceedings of the 2017 CHI Conference Extended Abstracts on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (Denver, Colorado, USA) (*CHI EA '17*). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 2915–2921. doi:10.1145/3027063.3053180
- [80] Steven Schmidt, Patrick Ehrenbrink, Benjamin Weiss, Jan-Niklas Voigt-Antons, Tanja Kojic, Andrew Johnston, and Sebastian Möller. 2018. Impact of Virtual Environments on Motivation and Engagement During Exergames. In *2018 Tenth International Conference on Quality of Multimedia Experience (QoMEX)*. 1–6. doi:10.1109/QoMEX.2018.8463389
- [81] Thomas Schubert, Frank Friedmann, and Holger Regenbrecht. 2001. The Experience of Presence: Factor Analytic Insights. *Presence: Teleoperators and Virtual Environments* 10, 3 (06 2001), 266–281. doi:10.1162/105474601300343603
- [82] Dale H Schunk. 2012. Learning Theories: An Educational Perspective. (2012).
- [83] Lindsay A Shaw, Jude Buckley, Paul M Corballis, Christof Lutteroth, and Burkhard C Wünsche. 2016. Competition and cooperation with virtual players in an exergame. *PeerJ Computer Science* 2 (2016), e92. doi:10.7717/peerj-cs.92
- [84] Mel Slater. 2009. Place illusion and plausibility can lead to realistic behaviour in immersive virtual environments. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 364, 1535 (2009), 3549–3557. doi:10.1098/rstb.2009.0138
- [85] Mel Slater and Maria V. Sanchez-Vives. 2016. Enhancing Our Lives with Immersive Virtual Reality. *Frontiers in Robotics and AI* 3 (2016), 47 pages. doi:10.3389/frobt.2016.00074
- [86] Mel Slater, Bernhard Spanlang, Maria V. Sanchez-Vives, and Olaf Blanke. 2010. First Person Experience of Body Transfer in Virtual Reality. *PLOS ONE* 5, 5 (05 2010), 1–9. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0010564
- [87] Frank Steinicke. 2016. *Being really virtual*. Springer, Berlin, Germany. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-43078-2
- [88] Philipp Sykownik, Katharina Emmerich, and Maic Masuch. 2018. Exploring Patterns of Shared Control in Digital Multiplayer Games. In *Advances in Computer Entertainment Technology*, Adrian David Cheok, Masahiko Inami, and Teresa Romão (Eds.). Springer International Publishing, Cham, 847–867.
- [89] Philipp Sykownik, Sukran Karaosmanoglu, Katharina Emmerich, Frank Steinicke, and Maic Masuch. 2023. VR Almost There: Simulating Co-located Multiplayer Experiences in Social Virtual Reality. In *Proceedings of the 2023 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (Hamburg, Germany) (*CHI '23*). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, Article 789, 19 pages. doi:10.1145/3544548.3581230
- [90] Unity Technologies. 2024. Unity Real-Time Development Platform. <https://unity.com/> LTS Release 2022.3.33f1. 12 June 2024. <https://unity.com/releases/editor/qa/lts-releases?version=2022.3>.
- [91] Edward Lee Thorndike. 1913. *The psychology of learning*. Vol. 2. Teachers College, Columbia University.
- [92] Charlène Truong, Célia Ruffino, Alexandre Crognier, Christos Paizis, Lionel Crognier, and Charalambos Papaxanthis. 2023. Error-based and reinforcement learning in basketball free throw shooting. *Scientific Reports* 13, 1 (2023), 499. doi:10.1038/s41598-022-26568-2
- [93] Wen-Jie Tseng, Petros Dimitrios Kontrazis, Eric Lecolinet, Samuel Huron, and Jan Gugenheimer. 2024. Understanding Interaction and Breakouts of Safety Boundaries in Virtual Reality Through Mixed-Method Studies. In *2024 IEEE Conference Virtual Reality and 3D User Interfaces (VR)*. 482–492. doi:10.1109/VR58804.2024.00069
- [94] Tamara Van Gog, Fred Paas, Nadine Marcus, Paul Ayres, and John Sweller. 2009. The mirror neuron system and observational learning: Implications for the effectiveness of dynamic visualizations. *Educational Psychology Review* 21, 1 (2009), 21–30. doi:10.1007/s10648-008-9094-3
- [95] Black Box VR. 2022. *Black Box VR*. Game [VR]. Black Box VR, Boise, USA. <https://www.blackbox-vr.com/>.
- [96] Marilyn Domas White and Emily E Marsh. 2006. Content analysis: A flexible methodology. *Library trends* 55, 1 (2006), 22–45. doi:10.1353/lib.2006.0053
- [97] Matthew M White. 2014. *Learn to play: Designing tutorials for video games*. CRC Press.
- [98] Jacob O. Wobbrock and Julie A. Kientz. 2016. Research contributions in human-computer interaction. *Interactions* 23, 3 (April 2016), 38–44. doi:10.1145/2907069
- [99] World Health Organization. 2022. *Global status report on physical activity 2022*. World Health Organization. <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240059153> (visited 4 September 2023).
- [100] World Health Organization. 2024. Physical Activity. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/physical-activity> Accessed: 01.09.2024.
- [101] Wenge Xu, Hai-Ning Liang, Kangyou Yu, and Nilufar Baghaei. 2021. Effect of Gameplay Uncertainty, Display Type, and Age on Virtual Reality Exergames. In *Proceedings of the 2021 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (Yokohama, Japan) (*CHI '21*). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, Article 439, 14 pages. doi:10.1145/3411764.3445801
- [102] Soojeong Yoo and Judy Kay. 2016. VRrun: running-in-place virtual reality exergame. In *Proceedings of the 28th Australian Conference on Computer-Human Interaction* (Launceston, Tasmania, Australia) (*OzCHI '16*). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 562–566. doi:10.1145/3010915.3010987
- [103] Hongyu Zhou, Treshan Ayes, Chenyu Fan, Zhanna Sarsenbayeva, and Anusha Withana. 2024. CoplayingVR: Understanding User Experience in Shared Control in Virtual Reality. *Proc. ACM Interact. Mob. Wearable Ubiquitous Technol.* 8, 3, Article 148 (Sept. 2024), 25 pages. doi:10.1145/3678508